

SOLAR COLLECTOR EFFICIENCY: Analysis and Application

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ABSTRACT

Solar energy as a source of renewable energy has been acknowledged to be a potential source of heat for domestic and industrial purposes. This paper analyzes the efficiency of different solar collectors and the determining factors affecting the efficiency of collectors, and presents them as pre-determining factors in the choice of collectors at the user end for cost and operational effectiveness.

KEYWORDS: Solar Insolation, Solar Collector Efficiency, Solar Energy Measurement, Temperature Belt.

INTRODUCTION

DEFINITION

Solar energy is a radiant energy from the sun which travels in form of electromagnetic radiation. The sun produces energy through a thermonuclear process that converts hydrogen into helium emitting heat and electromagnetic radiation, Illekhana (2007), Uppal, S.L. & Rao, V. (2009). According to Illekhana (2007), Nigeria for instance is situated in the high solar radiation belt of the world, receiving an average insolation level of about 7.0kWh/m³/day in the far north and about 3.5kWh/m²/day in the coastal latitudes, Illekhana (2007). Solar energy efficiency is usually at maximum when it is perpendicular on a plane along its path (i.e. when it is directly overhead). Other variables that affect the efficiency of the energy received from the sun include; angular position of the sun to the atmosphere, latitude, time of the day, season of the year and other minor considerations.

Solar collector efficiency can be defined as the ratio of usable thermal energy to received solar energy. Optical and thermal losses affect the efficiency of a solar collector, while conversion factor or optical efficiency indicates the percentage of the penetrating solar rays on the collector cover (transmission) and the percentage being absorbed. The heat loss is indicated by the thermal loss factor or k-value. This is given in watt per m², collector surface and the particular temperature difference (°C) between the absorber and its surroundings. The higher the temperature difference, the more heat is lost. Above a specific temperature difference, the amount of heat loss equals the energy yield of the collector, so that no energy at all is delivered to the solar circulation system. A good collector will have a high conversion factor and a low k-value (http://www.daviddarling.info/encyclopedia/S/AE_solar_collector.html).

ABSORBER: A material used in solar collectors that absorb incoming solar radiation and converts it to thermal energy. The performance characteristics of an absorber (absorptivity) determines its ability to absorb its maximum solar energy Schwaller,(1996).

MATERIAL AND METHODS/EXPERIMENT

SOLAR ENERGY MEASUREMENT AND EFFICIENCY

For more accuracy, the following factors were considered in the analysis of solar collector efficiency.

- **The Solar Constant:** This is the amount of energy reaching the outer edge of the earth's atmosphere Schwaller,(1996). This is measured as Btu (British Thermal Unit) striking a certain area in a specific time. Being a constant, it is measured to be 4,290 Btu/m²/h or an equivalent of 1,354W/m² (i.e. 1.5 horsepower/square yard).
- **Insolation:** This is radiation received per unit area for a given unit of time on the surface of the earth also known as incident solar radiation. Insolation has been measured in several units but the most common is the

- Btu/square foot/hour. This figure can be conveniently measured using an insolation meter held perpendicular to the sun's radiation. Studies show that insolation is a more useful tool for determining solar collectors efficiency than solar constant because it is a measure of the earth's surface and not the outer limits of the atmosphere. Air density, degree of cloud cover, geographical location, and time of the day, ambient temperature and angle of the sun are dependent variables that affect insolation. Insolation received at the earth's surface can range from 0 to about 360 Btu/ft²/hr, Schwaller,(1996). Ideally, if all insolation were to be captured without any loss, solar collectors would be said to be 100 percent efficient which in practice is not obtainable.
- Langley: This is another term used when calculations for a long period (say in years) are needed; it is measured in calories per centimeter squared. According to United States Weather Bureau which uses Langley to study weather pattern, one Langley is equivalent to one gram calorie per square meter of irradiated surface (221 Btu/ft²/hr).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following factors were considered important in determining the efficiency of solar collectors. Although the variations and relations of these factors are complex, it is important to note that each factor is important in its own consideration. Some of these variables include;

1. The design and materials of the collector (e.g glazing), amount of insulation, type of absorber surface to collect the incoming solar radiation.
2. The (outside) ambient temperature.
3. The wind velocity.
4. The inlet and outlet temperature difference of the fluid flowing through a collector (http://www.apricus.com/html/solar_collector_efficiency.htm).

Each of these factors is important when considering design, purchase, building and installing solar system with high efficiency. Considering the outlined factors above, an approximate calculation technique for measuring solar collector efficiency was employed [Table 1].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Step One: Typical ambient condition - A clear day around solar noon,

Step Two: The inlet and outlet temperatures of the collectors determined as follows:

Secure one thermometer in the inlet duct and one in the outlet duct (e.g. tape them in place), ensuring that the bulb or active part of the sensor is near the middle of the flow and that the sensor was not getting direct sunlight on it; Make sure the temperature sensor does not impede the air flow to any significant degree. A couple of dime store thermometers will work fine.

Step Three: The average air flow at the outlet vent determined as follows:

Measure the air flow velocity at the outlet duct. If the duct is large, measure the velocity in several places and take the average. You may also measure the flow by timing how long it takes to fill up a large plastic garbage bag of known size. If you are getting a lot of fluctuation in the velocity reading, try taking ten readings at fixed intervals (e.g. every 5 seconds) and average them. This velocity should really be corrected for the fact that velocities near the duct edges are slower than the center. The measurement is repeated three times. For example, one set at 5 minutes before noon, a 2nd at noon, and a 3rd 5 minutes after noon. Any readings that are widely different from the others are disregarded. Average the rest.

RESULTS

In a similar effort, Apricus (www.apricus.com) suggested a formula for the variables in calculating efficiency of solar collectors as;

$$h(x) = h_0 - a_1(x) - a_2.G(x)^2 \quad \text{--- where } [x = \frac{T_m - T_a}{G}]$$

The three performance variables for the Apricus solar collector (for metric calculations, based on absorber area): Conversion Factor: $h_0 = 0.717$, Loss Coefficient: $a_1 = 1.52 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}^2)$ and Loss Coefficient: $a_2 = 0.0085 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}^2)$. As well as the three performance variables shown above, insolation level (G) in Watts/m^2 , ambient temperatures (T_a) and average manifold temperature (T_m). These values give the value x. In real time application for instance, take a convenient time of the day say 2:40pm; ambient temperature of 25°C (77°F); average water temp [($T_{\text{inlet}} + T_{\text{exit}}$)/2] of 50°C (122°F); insolation level of $800 \text{ Watts}/\text{m}^2$ ($252 \text{ Btu}/\text{ft}^2$). $x = (50 - 25)/800 = 0.03125$ Now enter all the values into the formula:

$$h(x) = 0.717 - (1.52 * 0.03125) - (0.0085 * 800 * 0.03125^2) \quad \eta(x) = 0.717 - 0.0475 - 0.0066 = 0.663.$$

The solar conversion efficiency for that specific point in time and set of environmental conditions is 66.3%. That is: 66.3% of the energy provided by the sun is actually used to heat the water. Based on the assumption that those three environmental factors (G, T_m and T_a) are stable for a period of one hour, then $800 \times 0.663 = 530.4$ Watts of energy per m^2 of absorber area will be used to heat the water ($168 \text{ Btu}/\text{ft}^2$). 530.4 Watts is equivalent to 456kcal, which could heat 100L of water by 4.56°C (20 Gallons by 10.9°F) (<http://www.solarexpert.com/heatpanel.html>).

For a more accurate measurement, insolation can be measured with an insolation meter which reads insolation in $\text{Btu}/\text{ft}^2/\text{hr}$ and it is held perpendicular to the sun's radiation during operation. Schwaller,(1996).

A simulation of the above collection efficiency formula provided by apricus shows a related performance of a solar collector using different insolation levels (as shown in Table 1).

Table 1: Data sheet for different insolation levels (simulation of apricus data www.apricus.com)

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
2	EFFICIENCY	$h(x)$	T_m	T_a	G	h_0	$a_1(x)$	$a_2.G(x)^2$	$T_m - T_a$	(x)
3	71.7	0.717	5	5	800	0.717	0	0	0	0
4	69.7	0.6969375	20	10	800	0.717	0.019	0.0010625	10	0.0125
5	67.5	0.67475	40	20	800	0.717	0.038	0.00425	20	0.025
6	65.0	0.6504375	50	20	800	0.717	0.057	0.0095625	30	0.0375
7	62.4	0.624	70	30	800	0.717	0.076	0.017	40	0.05
8	59.5	0.5954375	90	40	800	0.717	0.095	0.0265625	50	0.0625
9	59.5	0.5954375	100	50	800	0.717	0.095	0.0265625	50	0.0625
10		G AT 600								
11	71.7	0.717	5	5	600	0.717	0	0	0	0
12	69.0	0.689777778	20	10	600	0.717	0.025	0.0018889	10	0.0167
13	65.9	0.658777778	40	20	600	0.717	0.051	0.0075556	20	0.0333
14	62.4	0.624	50	20	600	0.717	0.076	0.017	30	0.05
15	58.5	0.585444444	70	30	600	0.717	0.101	0.0302222	40	0.0667
16	54.3	0.543111111	90	40	600	0.717	0.127	0.0472222	50	0.0833
17	54.3	0.543111111	100	50	600	0.717	0.127	0.0472222	50	0.0833
18		G AT 400								
19	71.7	0.717	5	5	400	0.717	0	0	0	0
20	67.5	0.67475	20	10	400	0.717	0.038	0.00425	10	0.025
21	62.4	0.624	40	20	400	0.717	0.076	0.017	20	0.05
22	56.5	0.56475	50	20	400	0.717	0.114	0.03825	30	0.075
23	49.7	0.497	70	30	400	0.717	0.152	0.068	40	0.1
24	42.1	0.42075	90	40	400	0.717	0.19	0.10625	50	0.125
25	42.1	0.42075	100	50	400	0.717	0.19	0.10625	50	0.125
26										

Fig 1: A plot of Efficiency against Temperatures change for different insolation levels (simulation of apricus data www.apricus.com).

A plot of the above data in consideration of different insolation level provides a chart similar to that shown in Table 1. The above plot and information applies to all collectors but different a efficiency is obtained for different absorber systems. Ambient temperature is at the average hence it can fluctuate. Climatic condition affects the insolation and angular positioning (normally perpendicular to sun radiation) affects the insolation level also. All these and other factors contribute to the fluctuation of figures obtained as efficiency of the collector.

DISCUSSION

EFFICIENCY AND COLLECTOR SYSTEMS

As can be seen from the plot in Fig 1, efficiency of a collector is a function of the temperature difference (which is a function of the absorber system). Uppal, S.L. & Rao, V. (2009) and the insolation level. For different temperature zones and heating need of the user, different types of collectors with different efficiencies exist to suite the need and financial power of the user. Solar collectors can be classified according to the average temperature range over which they are intended to be used, and can be used effectively. These classifications are: "low temperature", "medium temperature" and "high temperature" (www.energisticsystems.us). For the purpose of installation and use, high temperature belt regions will find low temperature collectors and medium temperature collector more appropriate, while users at the low temperature belt will be more at home with high temperature collectors which are more expensive.

Low Temperature Collectors

Low temperature solar collectors are typically unglazed flat plate collectors, intended to operate at temperatures from 5 to 30 °F above ambient temperature. Low temperature liquid collectors are used for swimming pool heating and Crop drying. Unglazed collectors with aluminum absorber plates and copper water passages appear to be most cost effective over the typical metal collector having a lifetime of 20 years or more. All-copper collectors for swimming pool heating also work well, but are generally more expensive for the same performance characteristics. Copper is preferred over any other metal for water passages because of its high conductivity and compatibility with water. Almost all other metals must be separated from direct contact with the water being heated by a heat exchanger, which seriously reduces the collector efficiency (www.energisticsystems.us).

Medium Temperature Collectors

Medium temperature collectors typically are flat-plate collectors, enclosed in an insulated case, with one or two glazing. The intended temperature range of operation is from about 15 to 200 °F above ambient temperature. For the lower end of this range, single-glazed collectors with non-selective absorber plates are most cost effective. Typical applications include water heating, space heating and some medium temperature industrial heating. (www.energisticsystems.us).

High Temperature Collectors

High temperature collectors include some overlap from flat plate collectors in the medium temperature range, with selective absorber plates and heavy insulation, and may have temperature capabilities enhanced in installation by being mounted in a sun-tracking system (www.energisticsystems.us). Many other variations of high temperature collectors include evacuated-tube flat plate types, parabolic dish reflector types, parabolic trough types and modified parabola types. Most high temperature collectors depend on some type of sun tracking, in one or two axes, for effective operation. Tracking collectors are used to a small extent for domestic water heating and space heating, but are limited in cost effectiveness and reliability by the complexities of the tracking mechanisms, where used. Other uses are highly specialized, such as in absorption cooling systems, and applications where steam must be generated or very high temperatures are required with lowering of efficiency. Parabolic and other types of focusing collectors do not respond to indirect solar radiation, and collect little or no heat when the sun is obscured enough to prevent a clear shadow from being thrown. Conversely, flat plate collectors respond to radiation from all directions, and will collect diffuse radiation energy of as much as 30% of normal direct energy when there is no visible shadow Uppal, S.L. & Rao, V. (2009).

To a very great extent, the choice of collectors depends on the operating temperature, insolation level and purpose. Kalogirou (2008), shown in Tables 1 and 2 are summaries of collector types, its operating temperatures and insolation levels that gives an estimate of best performance after a proper evaluation of the determining factors.

Table 2: Collector classification according to purpose and operating temperature. Courtesy of *Energy Systems LLC*. www.energisticsystems.us.

CATEGORY		HEATING APPLICATION	COLLECTOR TYPE INVOLVED
	T inlet – Tambient		
A	-5 ⁰ C	-9 ⁰ F	LOW TEMPERARTURE COLLECTOR
B	5 ⁰ C	9 ⁰ F	
C	20 ⁰ C	36 ⁰ F	MEDIUM TEMPERATURE COLLECTOR
D	50 ⁰ C	90 ⁰ F	
E	90 ⁰ C	144 ⁰ F	HIGH TEMPERATURE COLLECTOR

In a similar effort, Energy systems estimated insolation level for different climatic conditions as

Table 3: Insolation Level for different Climatic conditions ([www. Energisticsystems.us](http://www.Energisticsystems.us)).

CATEGORY	SOLAR INSOLATION LEVEL
Clear Day	2000 BTU/ft ² /Day, 6.39kWh/m ² /Day
Mildly Cloudy Day	1500 BTU/ft ² /Day, 4.72kWh/m ² /Day
Cloudy Day	1000 BTU/ft ² /Day, 3.06kWh/m ² /Day

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the efficiencies of different types of solar collectors has been presented. From the analysis it is obvious that it is more appropriate and cost effective to understand the temperature belt of your location before installing and using a particular collector type, since not all collectors are suitable for every location and purpose. Users in the high temperature belt (Nigeria for instance with an insolation level of 7.0kWh/m²/day in the far north and about 3.5kWh/m²/day in the coastal latitudes) will not have need for high temperature collectors (unless for industrial purposes) instead, a low temperature collector for most time of the year and probably a medium temperature collector for dry and cold seasons will be more appropriate.

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